

Flexible Link Long Reach Manipulator with Lightweight Dual Arm: Soft-Collision Detection, Reaction, and Obstacle Localization

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Abstract— This paper proposes the application of long reach manipulators (LRM) in aerial manipulation, attaching a human size and lightweight dual arm at the tip of a flexible link installed at the base of the aerial platform. This configuration extends the reach and the volume of operation of the manipulator, whose workspace is constrained by the propellers and the landing gear, increasing also safety during the physical interactions on flight between the aerial robot and the environment. The deflection of the flexible link is exploited for collision detection and obstacle localization, allowing also the control of the contact force exerted by the arms. These capabilities are supported by a vision system that measures the deflection at the tip. Undesired oscillations of the link are suppressed generating a coordinated motion with the arms. Experiments in a fixed base test bench are conducted for validating the developed functionalities.

I. INTRODUCTION

The application of aerial manipulators to inspection and maintenance tasks in industrial environments [1] is affected by the proximity between the blades of the aerial platform, either multirotors [2][3][4] or autonomous helicopters [5][6], and the obstacles. The operation of the manipulator is also limited, as its reach is typically inside the perimeter of the blades, and the landing gear reduces significantly its workspace. Additionally, the interaction wrenches exerted over the manipulator during the operation on flight might compromise stability of the aerial platform [7] if the forces are rigidly propagated through a stiff-joint manipulator, as in a peg-in-hole task [8]. In this sense, mechanical compliance [9][10] increases the tolerance against small perturbations in contact situations, and thus, the reaction time for their compensation is higher. This feature, consisting of introducing an elastic element between the actuators and the output links, has been exploited in the estimation and control of the contact forces in lightweight arms [11], implementing methods for soft-collision detection and reaction [11][12].

Space robotics [13][14], nuclear waste cleanup, and civil infrastructure inspection and maintenance [15] are some usual application examples where the necessity to perform certain manipulation operations far away from the base of the robot has motivated the development of long reach manipulators (LRM) in the so called macro-micro configuration. However, achieving accurate position control of aerial vehicles becomes a hard task due to the dynamic coupling between the flexible link (macro part) and the dexterous manipulator installed at the tip (micro part), as any impact or contact force [16] or even the contactless motion of the arms [17] will cause a significant reaction of the flexible link that should be suppressed [18][19]. Although strain gauges are widely used in the measurement of link deflection, vision sensors have been applied for position

control [20], giving direct and accurate measurements in one or two axes [21], resulting also in simpler setups.

The main contribution of this paper is the development and experimental validation of three capabilities in a flexible long reach manipulator with a lightweight dual arm installed at the tip: 1) vibration suppression, 2) contact force control, and 3) obstacle detection and localization. This work evaluates the possibility of integrating a LRM in aerial platforms, motivated by the convenience of increasing the range and workspace of the manipulator (see Figure 1), whose motion is constrained by the landing gear and the propellers. The use of a LRM also contributes to increase safety in the realization of certain tasks involving physical interaction with the environment. The three functionalities are supported by a vision system that measures the deflection of the tip at 100 Hz, proposing a method for vibration suppression coordinating the motion of the arms.

This work considers a dual arm manipulator since there are a wide variety of operations that cannot be handled by a single arm, such as grasping large objects, transportation or retrieval of two sensors, eye-in-hand camera operation, or operating one arm while the other is grabbed at a fixed point. Unlike space manipulators [13][14], the lightweight dual arm considered in this work has been specifically designed for its integration in multi-rotor vehicles and tested on flight [23].

Figure 1. Dual arm aerial manipulation robot with flexible, long reach link. The batteries in the back act as counterweight of the arms. The flexible LRM increases safety in the physical interactions with the environment.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the flexible LRM with the lightweight dual arm and its potential use in aerial manipulation. Section III covers the kinematics and dynamics of the system, and Section IV details the developed capabilities. The experimental results are shown in Section V, presenting the conclusions in Section VI.

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II. FLEXIBLE LRM WITH LIGHTWEIGHT DUAL ARM

A. Motivation

As mentioned before, the dexterity, workspace and reach of a robotic manipulator integrated in an aerial platform, either multirotor or helicopter, is strongly constrained by the landing gear and the propellers. Extending the reach of the manipulator with a flexible link increases safety, not only because the risk of impact between the propellers and the obstacles is lower, but also because the mechanical flexibility avoids that contact forces are rigidly propagated to the aerial platform. In this way, the controller of the aerial platform has more time to react to the perturbations associated to the physical interaction during the operation on flight. However, the proposed configuration presents a number of drawbacks. On the one hand, the total weight of the robot increases slightly due to the flexible link. The displacement of the mass also has to be compensated, using for example the batteries as counterweight [4]. Figure 1 illustrates this concept with the proposed prototype of dual arm LRM installed at the base of a hexarotor. On the other hand, the control of the aerial platform becomes more complex since the displacement of the aerial platform and the motion of the arms are strongly coupled with the flexible link, especially under the effect of lateral accelerations and rotations in the yaw angle which induce oscillations in the flexible link.

B. System Description

The developed prototype of flexible LRM with lightweight and human size dual arm at the tip can be seen in Figure 2. The flexible link consists of an $800 \times 45 \times 3$ mm size aluminum profile, weighting 0.3 kg, with its flat surface orthogonal to the direction of gravity. The dual arm system provides 5 DOF per arm, three for end effector positioning (shoulder yaw at the base, followed by shoulder pitch and elbow pitch) and two for orientation (wrist roll and pitch), although these two are not exploited in this paper. The mechanical specifications are summarized in Table 1. The dual arm, described in more detail in [23], is designed for aerial manipulation with multirotors, so special attention has been paid in reducing as much as possible the total mass and inertia. For that reason most part of the mass, which corresponds to the servos, is placed close to the shoulder structure. The frame of the arms is manufactured in anodized aluminum, using igus® EFOM-08 flange bearings to support the rotation of the links and protect the servos against impacts.

Figure 2. Lightweight and human size dual arm system installed at the tip of a 80 cm length flexible link (left). A Prosilica GC 1380H camera at the base provides direct measurement of tip deflection (right).

Table 1. Specifications of the dual arm system

Total mass	1.8 [kg]	
Max. lift load	0.75 [kg] per arm	
Size	Forearm length L_1 : 25 [cm]	
	Upper arm length L_2 : 25 [cm]	
	Separation between arms D : 25 [cm]	
Rotation range	Shoulder yaw	± 90 [deg]
	Shoulder pitch	± 90 [deg]
	Elbow pitch	10 – 150 [deg]
Actuators	Herkulex Servos, model DRS-0101, DRS-0402, DRS-0602	

A Prosilica GC 1380H camera installed at the base of the LRM is focused in a marker placed at the back of the shoulder structure. It is used as reference to measure the flexible link tip deflection. The marker is a 10 mm \varnothing black dot drawn over a 300×50 mm size white panel that acts as background. In this way, the camera provides direct measurement of tip deflection with high accuracy and reliability. Since the flat surface of the flexible link is orthogonal to the direction of gravity, the beam will not be affected by long term deformations due to this force in the vertical axis. However, a torsional component along the axis of the link was observed when the motion of the arms is asymmetric around this axis. The torsional deflection can be also measured with the vision system adding a second marker.

C. Vision Sensor

The developed functionalities of the dual arm LRM are based on the high frame rate vision system that provides direct measurement of tip deflection. This sensor, whose features are listed in Table 2, consists of the Prosilica camera and a marker detector software module executed within the main program that controls the manipulator. This program, coded in C++, makes use of the *OpenCV 2.4.2* library for image acquisition and processing. The Canny edge detector is applied over each grabbed frame for obtaining the contours found on the image. Geometrical information (contour length and area) is used for rejecting false positives in the detection. The region of interest (ROI) of the camera was set to the minimum size needed, 500×100 pixels, achieving a frame rate up to 100 FPS, enough to track the marker that oscillates at 0.6 Hz.

Table 2. Specifications of the vision sensor for tip deflection measurement.

Frame rate	100 [FPS]
Resolution	500×100 [pixels]
Distance to marker	80 [cm]
Max. deflection range	15 [cm]
Accuracy	0.28 [mm/pixel]
Delay	15 [ms]

III. MODELING

A. Kinematic Model

In an aerial manipulation system, three reference frames are usually defined: the Earth fixed frame $\{E\}$, the UAV base frame $\{B\}$, and the manipulator frame $\{M\}$, denoting as T_M^B and $T_B^E \in \mathcal{R}^{4 \times 4}$ to the respective transformation matrices. For

convenience, the points of interest for the manipulation task will be defined in the reference frame of the manipulator. If $\mathbf{p}^M = [x, y, z, 1]^T$ represents a certain target point in $\{\mathbf{M}\}$, then the same point can be expressed in the inertial frame $\{\mathbf{E}\}$ in the following way, more suitable during the approaching phase:

$$\mathbf{p}^E = \mathbf{T}_B^E \cdot \mathbf{p}^B = \mathbf{T}_B^E \cdot (\mathbf{T}_M^B \cdot \mathbf{p}^M) \quad (1)$$

The kinematic model of the flexible LRM with the dual arm prototype at the tip is represented in Figure 3. As seen, the dual arm system suffers a translation and a slight rotation due to the deflection of the flexible link, so \mathbf{T}_M^B will depend on the flexible link tip deflection $w(t, L)$, where L is the flexible link length. Considering only the positioning joints, the kinematic configuration of the dual arm consists of the shoulder yaw joint at the base followed by the shoulder pitch and elbow pitch joints. The corresponding joint angles for both left and right arms will be denoted as θ_1^{LR} , θ_2^{LR} and θ_3^{LR} . The Cartesian position of the wrist point is given by:

$$\mathbf{p}_{wrist}^{LR} = \begin{bmatrix} r(\theta_2^{LR}, \theta_3^{LR}) \cdot \cos(\theta_1^{LR}) \\ D/2 \pm r(\theta_2^{LR}, \theta_3^{LR}) \cdot \sin(\theta_1^{LR}) \\ -L_1 \cdot \cos(\theta_2^{LR}) - L_2 \cdot \cos(\theta_2^{LR} + \theta_3^{LR}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here L_1 , L_2 and D represent the upper arm and forearm lengths, and the separation between both arms, respectively. The term $r(\theta_2, \theta_3)$ is defined as follows:

$$r(\theta_2, \theta_3) = L_1 \cdot \sin(\theta_2) + L_2 \sin(\theta_2 + \theta_3) \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. Kinematic model of the dual arm with flexible LRM aerial robot.

This configuration provides analytical solution for the inverse kinematics. The joint angles can be easily obtained from the Cartesian position of the wrist point:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_1^{LR} \\ \theta_2^{LR} \\ \theta_3^{LR} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{atan2}(y_{LR} \mp D/2, x_{LR}) \\ \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{x_{LR}^2 + (y_{LR} \mp D/2)^2 + z_{LR}^2 + L_1^2 - L_2^2}{2 \cdot L_1 \cdot \sqrt{x_{LR}^2 + (y_{LR} \mp D/2)^2}} \right) \\ \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{x_{LR}^2 + (y_{LR} \mp D/2)^2 + z_{LR}^2 - L_1^2 - L_2^2}{2 \cdot L_1 \cdot L_2} \right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

B. Flexible Link Dynamics

The dynamic behavior of a flexible link is derived from the Lagrangian and the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory [22]. According to the assumed-modes method, the deflection of the flexible link can be expressed as the sum of an infinite number of vibration modes:

$$w(t, x) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \varphi_i(x) \cdot \delta_i(t) \quad , \quad x \in [0, L] \quad (5)$$

Here $\varphi_i(x)$ is the modal shape function and $\delta_i(t)$ is the generalized coordinate of the i -th vibration mode. Each vibration mode has associated a frequency that depends on the mechanical parameters of the link and the tip. The positioning accuracy of the arms is determined mainly by the first mode, considering this approximation in the developed capabilities:

$$w(t, L) \approx \varphi_1(L) \cdot \delta_1(t) \quad (6)$$

The deflection of flexible link caused by an external force $f(t)$ applied at the tip can be modeled as mass-damper-spring system in the following form [18]:

$$m_1 \ddot{\delta}_1(t) + d_1 \dot{\delta}_1(t) + k_1 \delta_1(t) = f(t) \quad (7)$$

The friction d_1 and elastic constant k_1 parameters can be obtained experimentally from the impulsive response, and the generalized mass m_1 from the CAD model. As most part of the mass of the dual arm system is placed close to the shoulder frame, the variation of these parameters due to changes in joint position is not significant. The dynamic coupling between the dual arm and the flexible link is described in next subsection.

C. Dynamic Coupling between Dual Arm and Flexible Link

The mechanical structure of the flexible LRM shown in Figure 2 is similar to the one studied in [13]. The dynamic model of the compound can be written in the following form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} m_1 & \mathbf{H}_{bm} \\ \mathbf{H}_{bm}^T & \mathbf{H}_m \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\delta}_1 \\ \ddot{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} d_1 \dot{\delta}_1 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} k_1 \delta_1 \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_g \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c_b \\ \mathbf{c}_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f \\ \boldsymbol{\tau} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Here $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathcal{R}^6$ are the generalized coordinates and the joint torque of the dual arm system, respectively, whereas $\boldsymbol{\tau}_g \in \mathcal{R}^6$ is the gravity term affecting the shoulder pitch and elbow pitch joints. Note from Figure 3 that gravity does not affect to the flexible link as long as \mathbf{Z}_B and the gravity vector are parallel. Matrices $\mathbf{H}_m \in \mathcal{R}^{6 \times 6}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{bm} \in \mathcal{R}^{1 \times 6}$ represent the inertia of the dual arm and the coupling inertia matrix between the dual arm and the flexible link. Finally, c_b and $\mathbf{c}_m \in \mathcal{R}^6$ are nonlinear terms that depend on deflection and joint speed.

IV. CAPABILITIES IN A FLEXIBLE LRM WITH DUAL ARM

A. Vibration Suppression based on Zero-Cross Detection

The proposed method for vibration suppression must cope with the technological limitations of the Herkulex servos used in the arms, as these low cost actuators, which are currently the best solution for building low weight manipulators, do not allow direct feedback or control of joint acceleration or torque, and the update rate is <100 Hz. The servos are commanded in position and play time, sending a data packet to each of them with the desired goal position and duration of the motion. The internal controller generates then a trapezoidal velocity profile that satisfies these two requirements.

The proposed method for vibration suppression makes use of the vision system for identifying on-line the maximum amplitude of the oscillation and the time instant in which the deflection crosses by zero. Let us consider the flexible link in free oscillation due to some impact, acceleration or force. The deflection of the tip will describe a sinusoidal signal that can be expressed in the following way:

$$w(t, L) = W_0 \cdot e^{-d_1 \cdot t} \cdot \sin(\omega_1 \cdot t + \phi_0) \quad (9)$$

where W_0 is the initial amplitude of the oscillation, ω_1 is the natural frequency, d_1 is the damping coefficient, and ϕ_0 is the initial phase. The algorithm, described in Table 3, consists of an iterative process executed while the maximum amplitude of the deflection, W_{max} , is higher than the desired error W_ϵ . For each iteration, the program waits until a change in the sign of the deflection signal is detected. Meanwhile, the maximum amplitude of the oscillation is identified just evaluating the absolute value of the deflection signal. When the zero cross is detected, the shoulder yaw joint servos are commanded to a reference position $\theta_{1,ref}^{LR}$ that is proportional to the maximum deflection, with constant K , and that is 180 degree out of phase with respect to $w(t, L)$. The play time is set to a quarter of the oscillation period, that is, the remaining time before the tip deflection reaches again its maximum value. Phase φ indicates the direction of the deflection, whose value is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} w(t_0^-, L) < w(t_0^+, L) &\rightarrow \varphi = 0 \\ w(t_0^-, L) > w(t_0^+, L) &\rightarrow \varphi = 180 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where t_0^- and t_0^+ represent the time instants just before and just after the zero cross.

Table 3. Pseudocode implementing the vibration suppression method.

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while  $W_{max} < W_\epsilon$ 
   $W_{max} = 0$ ;
  while  $sign(w(t^-, L)) \neq sign(w(t, L))$ 
    If  $|w(t, L)| \geq W_{max} \rightarrow W_{max} = |w(t, L)|$ 
    MoveServo( $\theta_{1,ref}^{LR} = K \cdot W_{max} \cdot \cos(\varphi)$ , play time =  $\frac{T_1}{4}$ )
  end

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This method is model free [19] in the sense that gain K can be tuned empirically without requiring knowledge of the parameters of the dynamic model. The proof of stability is also simple and intuitive: as long as the energy injected by the arm(s) on each oscillation period, which depends on the adjustable parameter K , is lower than the mechanical energy of the oscillating mass within the same period, then the amplitude of the oscillation will tend to decrease.

B. Contact-based Obstacle Detection and Localization

Consider the situation depicted in Figure 4. Assuming that the only cause for flexible link tip deflection is the presence of an external force acting over any of the arms, then a simple collision detection method based on constant threshold can be applied for detecting the presence of an obstacle. During an initial scan phase, both arms move symmetrically with respect to the $X_B Z_B$ plane so the reaction forces along the direction of the deflection are cancelled. Following the criterion described in Table 4, it is even possible to infer in which side and in which arm the collision occurred taking into account the direction of rotation of the joints and the sign of the deflection. Here $w_{th} \sim 10$ [mm] is the collision detection threshold. This value is low enough to prevent that high contact forces arise (“soft” collision detection). In Figure 4, the collision in (2) causes a positive deflection while the right arm is rotation clock wise, inferring that there is an obstacle on the right side. The assumption regarding the source of the deflection requires that the motion of the arms do not cause any reaction force in

the direction of the deflection, what can be achieved if left and right arms move symmetrically around the plane of the link.

Figure 4. The dual arm system executes a scan for detecting obstacles, rotating the shoulder yaw joint until a collision occurs. The contact force causes a deflection in the flexible link and a reaction in the UAV.

Table 4. Criteria for identifying which arm and in which side a collision occurs based on flexible link tip deflection and the sign of the scan.

Left/Right arm rotation	Deflection	Affected arm/side
Counter clockwise/clockwise	$w(t, L) \leq -w_{th}$	Left arm, left side
	$w(t, L) \geq w_{th}$	Right arm, right side
Clockwise/counter clockwise	$w(t, L) \geq w_{th}$	Left arm, right side
	$w(t, L) \leq -w_{th}$	Right arm, left side

The obstacle detection capability can be easily extended in such a way that, known the position of the arm affected by the contact, it is possible to determine the position of the obstacle. Although it is expected that the aerial robot is equipped with vision and range sensors for navigation in narrow spaces, it is possible that these sensors are not reliable in certain situations, for example due to the lack of texture in the environments, obstacles out of the field of view or out of the detectable range. In this sense, the compliant contact sensor increases reliability.

In order to accurately localize the contact point, a two-step process will be executed, taking into account that the contact may occur in any point along the upper arm or forearm. In the first step, both arms are fully stretched ($\theta_2^{LR} = 90$, $\theta_3^{LR} = 0$) and perform a scan motion rotating the shoulder yaw joints from an initial value $\theta_1^{LR} = \pm\alpha_0$. This scan phase ends when the collision is detected, determining the scan angle $\theta_1^{LR} = \pm\beta$ for the second step. Starting now with the arms retracted, a new scan is performed around this angle with a certain amplitude $\Delta\beta \sim 5$ deg. The idea is to force that the first contact point is the end effector, stretching the arms on each iteration so the reach of the scan increases until the second collision occurs.

C. Contact Force Control

The vision sensor can be exploited to estimate and control the force applied over the Y_M axis (see Figure 3). Combining Equations (6) and (7), it is obtained a proportional relationship between the deflection at the tip and the contact force in this axis. Let us consider the situation depicted in Figure 4. The rotation around the shoulder yaw joint of the arm that is in contact with the environment will cause the displacement of the flexible link. Therefore, the contact force can be controlled by means of θ_1 , implementing a feedback control scheme as the one depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Contact force control scheme. The shoulder yaw joint determines the pushing force of the end effector against a surface in the direction of the flexible link tip deflection. The force is proportional to the tip deflection.

V. RESULTS

A. Vibration Suppression

In this experiment, the control method described in Section IV-A is applied for removing the oscillations in the flexible link tip. Figure 6 represents the tip deflection and the shoulder yaw joint speed for different values of gain K . The execution of the experiment is as follows. The system is initially in a rest state, with the arms stretched and parallel to the floor ($\theta_1 = 0$, $\theta_2 = 90$, $\theta_3 = 0$). At $t = 0$, the left arm generates a rotation motion around the shoulder yaw joint to inject energy into the flexible link, rotating from 0 to 45 deg in one second, going back to $\theta_1 = 0$ at $t = 2.2$ s. This excites the first vibration mode, causing an 50 mm oscillation at the tip, with 1.58 s period. Both parameters are measured online while the flexible link tip oscillates freely. At $t = 5$, the vibration suppression mode is enabled. In this moment, the deflection signal changes its sign (zero cross), so its phase is determined (0 deg in this case). Immediately the shoulder yaw actuators of both arms move in the same direction, generating a reaction force that partially cancels the oscillation. As it can be derived from Figure 6, smaller amplitudes of the reaction motion require a higher number of iterations for removing the oscillation. The value of the gain K defined in Table 3 was determined experimentally, although an initial guess can be obtained from the maximum rotation angle of the shoulder yaw joint ($\theta_3 < 90$ deg) and the maximum deflection at the tip of the flexible link ($w(t, L) < 75$ mm).

Figure 6. Flexible link tip deflection (top) and shoulder yaw joint speed (bottom) in the vibration suppression experiment for different compensation amplitudes. The left arm generates a disturbance between $t = 0$ and $t = 2.2$ seconds (red area). Vibration suppression enabled at $t = 5$ s (green line).

B. Collision Detection and Contact Force Control

The methods described in Section IV B-C for detecting obstacles close to the manipulator and controlling the contact force in terms of flexible link tip deflection are applied here. The dual arm system is initially in a rest state with both arms stretched and parallel to the floor ($\theta_1 = \mp 10$, $\theta_2 = 90$, $\theta_3 = 0$), with zero deflection. Figure 7 shows the evolution of the tip deflection (feedback, reference and threshold) along with the shoulder yaw joint angle of the left arm, and the two flags for enabling vibration suppression and force control. At $t = 5$ both arms start a scan motion rotating the shoulder yaw joint from $\theta_1 = -10$ to $\theta_1 = 60$ deg, going back to $\theta_1 = -10$ deg. At $t = 11.2$ s, during the second scan, the left arm impacts against a moving obstacle that appeared in its left side, causing an immediate deflection of the flexible link which is detected when the $w_{th} = 10$ mm threshold is exceeded. This value was determined experimentally taking into account the nominal error in the deflection signal. Once the impact is detected, both arms go to a collision-free position, enabling the vibration suppression mode at $t = 13.1$. Then, the left arm approaches slowly to the contact point, enabling the contact force control mode at $t = 32$ s, specifying a 25 mm tip deflection. When the left arm stops pushing the obstacle and goes back to $\theta_1 = 0$, the disturbance associated to the transition from contact to contactless state causes again the oscillation of the tip, which is removed enabling the vibration suppression mode.

Figure 7. Flexible link tip deflection measurement and reference (top), shoulder yaw joint angle (middle), and control flags (bottom) corresponding to the collision detection experiment with contact force control.

C. Obstacle Localization with Soft Collision Detection

The method described in Section IV-B intended to obstacle localization was implemented and tested experimentally. The trajectory of the wrist point of both left and right arms in the XY plane has been represented in Figure 8 along with the scan line (dashed) and the position of the obstacle (black dot). The arrows represent the direction of motion from the initial scan point, followed by the first scan that ends once the first contact point is detected, moment in which the scan line is determined. The second scan starts with the arms retracted, increasing the distance from the wrist point to the base of the arms in 100 mm steps until the obstacle is located. The evolution of the flexible link tip deflection signal can be seen in Figure 9. The events marked in red correspond to the impact of the left arm against the obstacle during the first and second scans, respectively.

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Figure 8. Trajectory followed by the wrist point of left and right arms for the obstacle localization experiment: first impact in the forearm of the left arm (1), and collision at the wrist point during the second scan (2).

Figure 9. Flexible link tip deflection and thresholds for collision detection. The two impacts of the left arm against the obstacle are marked. Vibration suppression is executed after the impacts for removing tip oscillation.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed the application of a flexible link long reach manipulator with a lightweight dual arm system at the tip for extending the dexterity and manipulation capability of an aerial manipulation system, exploiting compliance in the flexible link for increasing the safety during the execution of those operations or tasks involving physical contact with the environment. Experimental results in a fixed base test bench have been presented for evaluating the performance of the developed prototype, showing three capabilities: vibrations suppression, contact force control and obstacle localization. The derivation of the dynamic model of the whole aerial manipulator and the evaluation on flight with multirotor or autonomous helicopter platform is left as future work.

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